

Perspective Piece

Proponents of Harmonization between Body, Mind and Soul

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“The rhythm of the body, the melody of the mind and the harmony of the soul creates the symphony of life”.

B.K.S. Iyengar, a foremost Yoga teacher from India correlated the symphony of life with a balance of body, mind and soul in such a way that it answers most of the questions by people suffering from stressful lives. It must be understood that according to WHO constitution, health is defined as a complete well-being of mental, physical and social aspects of a person, not the absence of disability or disease (WHO, 1950). Not to forget that the aspect of soul is generally not considered in scientific world, this article steps forward initialising the understanding of soul as an integral part of human body in terms of philosophy as well as science. Considering the aspect of health sciences; a mind fully synchronised with the body and soul is a sign of having a greater intelligence than IQ and EQ as a mind convinced with current conditions of body and soul will be able to boost up the usage of intellect and wisdom in order to achieve greater and much effective results in terms of creativity, health and spiritual growth. One of the best ways adopted by greats of their time to achieve harmony is through meditation (Thera, 2014).

The Three Opinions

Taking in consideration, the interaction between the body and soul, in terms of its operations between one and the other and one over the other, there are three opinions (Bowne, 1887). The first opinion is called the physical influx in which the sensory organs receive incoming data from the world in forms of vision when it comes to the eye and sound waves when it comes to the ears; similarly, for the senses of touch, taste and smell. Since the organs carrying such senses receive firstly the impressions made by the direct interaction with the surroundings, these impressions trigger mind to think and will to act accordingly. Due to this reason, philosophers from ancient times believed that physical influx is a result derived from these organs and hence it enters the soul of a person.

The second opinion named as spiritual influx suggested by the law itself in order to illustrates the useful findings in this regard. However, soul is an important component of spirituality which demonstrates the inner substance of an individual. The important element of spiritual soul is purity, internal aspects and previous materials that human body possesses within its self. Further, the relationship between body and its soul is termed as spiritual influx as suggested by different scholars and previous researchers. Therefore, human body is nothing without these illusions because soul gets into the grosser with related aspects such as posterior, interior and exterior. The spiritual material cannot be reversed at any means by natural phenomenon. The human mind which has the functionality of memorizing the items, recall the previous scenarios and importantly thinks about certain situations and

accordingly react with respective surrounding. The things or different situations, in which we react or interact on daily basis, collectively developed the personality traits along with soul perspective.

The third opinion which determines or called as pre-established harmony is learning in different modern theories due to its purposeful findings in human nature. The misconceptions of the mind and its thinking process acts collectively at the same time and place with human body and its spiritual soul. The success factor hidden in influx spirituality is harmony that has the link with different or simultaneous operations. Initially, the minds think and then it gives substantial power to the speaking skills which human beings exhibits in their self. The establishment of these operations exclude all the components of power and energy as mind plays his role. The interaction of human soul with its body is not possible as it must operate with existing body with its soul and sometimes both operate collectively.

The Science of Soul

“The day science begins to study non-physical phenomenon, it will make progress in one decade than in all the previous centuries of its existence” – Nikola Tesla

Since the beginning of human awareness of soul, psychologically, a soul is considered to be the consciousness of a human body (Pereira, 2015). Taking this point in view, one can certainly deduce that consciousness is the driving force of the body which makes a body endorsing its existence in the universe. Different aspects of consciousness are defined and concluded by many researchers

throughout time. The presence of soul in a body is widely accepted and understood when a person dies; considering the fact that each and everything is present in a person essential to live, what makes a person die? A research by Duncan MacDougall in 1907 proved that there is a soul in a person's body and the soul has a weight of about 21grams (Roehner, 2010). In this experiment, MacDougall took a sample of 6 patients who were about to die and put them in an industrial sized weighing machine that can weigh any substance as little as 5.5 grams. When soul is departed by the body, the weight which was reduced from the body was recorded by MacDougall with other doctors from the hospital to be about 21 grams or approximately one ounce. Such discovery has put most of the scientists to think beyond material and hence the concept of body and mind synchronisation was tuned up to body, mind and soul harmonisation (Pandya, 2011).

The Proponents

Harmonisation between body and mind is taken through various concepts by psychologists, psychophysicologists and psychiatrists on accordance to their knowledge and experiences. A proponent is defined as something which advocates and supports in achievement of something. Considering the harmonisation of body, mind and soul, as it speaks of itself, would not be something which should be done through just one way; a person needs to get through multiple practices and multiple understandings in order to achieve harmony of body, mind and soul which would both differ and coincide with each other. A person is said to be in complete harmony when his/her body, mind and soul is completely utilised throughout the day before he/she sleeps and when he/she wakes up, he is optimised for his/her work. Such state is achieved when a person performs physical work in order to exhaust his/her body, analyses and attempts different intellectual tasks up to his/her limits to drain his/her mental energy and goes in a world of imagination to tire his/her soul. When a person goes through such processes during the time he or she is awake and sleeps afterwards, his/her body, mind and soul makes up a connection between each other in order to optimise to the fullest.

It is one of the easiest ways to achieve harmonisation between them. One other way to harmony is both psychological and philosophical and also advised by the author. In order to achieve harmony, firstly, one should be able to gain the state of peace throughout his/her existence and that is done by acceptance. As a person accepts everything which comes into his/her interaction, no matter if it impacts him/her good or bad, it will naturally allow him/her to gain state of peace within the body. In such condition, the person is harmonised with all the aspects of his/her existence, i.e. the body, mind and soul.

Conclusion

Since harmonisation of body, mind and soul is a wider study which cannot be confined in a single study, it must be noted that the aspects and concepts mentioned in this article are just drops in an entire ocean. One simply cannot claim to withhold all the knowledge of such harmonisation since there is a gradual increase in the understanding of body, mind and soul of a human body. One thing which we should think of is, to what level does the synchronisation of body, mind and soul extends to?

References

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